

LCpl. Brian Paul Kaess in the U.S. Marines in Cuba
by Brian Paul Kaess

I arrived via a flight from Chicago to Norfolk, then to Jacksonville, and then on to the U.S. Naval Base at Guantanamo Bay, Cuba, better known as 'Gitmo'. I almost missed the flight at Norfolk because of a late connection. My bag was late too. A Navy dude getting off the same plane, stated happily: 'Three more years of paradise!' A Marine Sgt. in the hangar on Leeward greeted us and took a close look at me because I was older and had an 'afternoon shadow' from all the travel. I had orders for Marine Detachment, Cuba, and that meant Marine Barracks, 'Gitmo.' We were here for a one year tour. I spent three months on the Leeward side, nine months on the Windward. I was assigned to Rifle Security Company (RSC) Leeward for the first three months and then S-3, HQ's Company, Marine Barracks for the last nine months- the latter assignment being on the Windward side. Windward was where most of the action was, but Leeward had excellent food for a small chow hall and I remember some of the murals with Leeward's nickname 'the Dark Side' written on it, basically because it could get really pitch black on Leeward at night. Plus, there was a beautiful view of the Caribbean at sunset on Leeward. Furthermore, I remember being on Marine Observation Post or MOP 1 when Coast Guard aircraft would swoop in low to land at the Airfield on Leeward, not far from our barracks. I would often salute the Aircraft as they were coming in low on their final descent. I guess that's what Marines do well.

Col. Bamford (from Nebraska) commanded Marine Barracks and I also met Major Aiken (a Vanderbilt grad) and Capt. Jewell, the Air Officer. Our Captain and CO on Leeward was Capt. Petrucci (son of a General) and our Platoon Sgt. was SSG Cross (heralded athlete), who joked once with the platoon that we might take 'Liberty' in Havana! He also had a number of Marines sing 'Happy Birthday' for me when I turned 30, practically in jest. Our Platoon Leader was 2nd Lt. Ring (who went to Texas A & M). He once tried to teach us how to apply explosives with black tar to enemy tanks, but it seemed like an almost futile idea, similar to becoming a Sapper! Our acting 1st Sgt. on Leeward was GySgt. McGovern (Former Recon) who would hang out near the ammo bunkers and tell people, 'This is how I'm going to win my Medal of Honor someday!' he would throw tantrums in front of the company formation that were memorable. The Marine Barracks Sgt. Major was a Vietnam Veteran – the 'scuttlebutt' being he had stabbed an NVA soldier to death who had jumped into his foxhole during the Tet Offensive. It was his decision to switch me to radio operator on the Windward side in January 1998 when Captain Wallace had noticed me falling behind on one of the speed marches and ordered me into his jeep. I guess it was hot that day. Care for the troops!

Our first week on the fenceline, I saw Cubans building machine gun bunkers in the middle of the No-Man's allowed, a brazen act, but still allowed since it was technically their land. On Leeward, we performed fenceline duty during Mission Week, unless the 'react vehicle' got involved. I remember lots of inspections. For RSC-Leeward, we handled five towers at MOP 1, MOP 3, MOP 8, MOP 13, MOP 18. I think I stood watch on all of them. We had specific rules of engagement and were taught a few words of Spanish that might be handy. They also showed us photographs, even of minefield victims, including Marines from times past. The Cubans would run patrols using various guideposts already stationed in the No-Man's Land. Civilians trying to flee Cuba might use the same posts, at their own peril. There were also minefields on the American side of the wire one had to be

careful about. But mostly the Cuban vehicles operated along the perimeter road hugging their side of the fenceline and that's what we were keenly observant on.

My next door roommates on Leeward were Nichols & Johnson at Leeward and my roommate on Leeward was Van Hoosen (from TN) and Antoine La Count (from GA) on the Windward side. I had a quicky, white dude for a roommate my first month on Windward, but I forgot his name. He told me his father had been a Marine who committed suicide later in life by jumping into an empty swimming pool head-first from an story. We both roared! Nichols & Johnson threw a party once in their room with some alcohol and high school chicks present and invited me in. When I realized what 'inappropriate' means, I walked right in and then walked right back out! Even the Colonel's daughter was dating a younger Marine. I would visit the beaches, library, & Naval Exchange (NEX) for pizza. There was also an Elementary School & High School. They even had a McDonald's on base. I checked out the weight room and swimming pools while on duty. I played basketball now and then at both basketball courts on Leeward and Windward. I really liked the scrambled eggs and pancakes with syrup (and occasional sausages) they would feed us on the fenceline or COC when we were too busy to fetch it ourselves. Gatorade was also readily available and was a common sight. They even had a Marina with watercraft. I think there was a small Officer's Club on Leeward, but that didn't stop unauthorized personnel from going there I heard since it was the only party hub on Leeward. There were even 'fenceline' tours for civilians, but at limited times. Gitmo had a combined population of about 2,500 persons, including military, DOD civilians, and dependents. The Marines were here to defend it all- from hilltop to swamp to tall grass to sandy beach.

On the Windward side, I was stationed with HQ's Company at the 'white house' on Marine Hill. I was assigned as a radio operator at Marine Barracks Command Operations Center, a sensitive position. GySgt. Jury was our NCOIC at S-3 and pretty much ran things. Capt. Sautee, SSG Paige, SSG Tejas (from Texas) and Sgt. George also worked in S-3. SSG Paige had been one of my recruiters in Chicago and was very positive. He took me once to the top of Marine Observation Post 1 along the coast and said to me, 'Well, Pfc. Kaess, here you are in Cuba!' I was promoted to Lance Corporal in October 1997. Jury gave sermons on Sundays as a sort of base Preacher. There was a Marine Sgt. (former Recon) who worked in S-3 and all the other Sgts. laughed at him because his woman nicknamed him 'pooky-bear'. Galaz (from AZ), Lamb (from CA), & Westover (from IA) were my buddies and I also worked with Sherman (from WA), Snow, Chad Beller (famous for his many wives), Riley (from NY), Theobald (from WA), Russell (from MS), Montgomery (an Army Vet) & Salamanca-Medina. Fleming and Knox were both from Texas and Fleming was the DM (Designated Marksman) for the Leeward Company, basically a sniper. Fleming was involved with some hazing, but no biggie. I hung out with Navy gals named Enke, Liz, & Heather. Beller had some weird story where he said he had killed three people in self-defense back home in Pennsylvania. He knew martial arts of some kind. If that story were true, I am not even sure the French Foreign Legion could hide him!

On our base were three companies of Marines, plenty of Navy personnel, including engineers, & a Navy Hospital. There were also Coast Guard AWACS aircraft, a U.S. Army Airborne Intelligence contingent, and a Special Forces Detachment, and a surprizing number of civilians. Marine Corps Intelligence was also present in Cuba and they had their own site. I remember a Coast Guard Cutter pulling into Gitmo for some sort of shore leave. I was often taking the ferry from the Leeward side to the Windward side to visit the hospital. Captain Chronin, a Navy Surgeon, was the 'Doc' who medically boarded me out

based on my right leg & finger injuries. He offered me elective surgery on my right leg but I turned him down. My brother Garret told me once, 'If you can walk, you don't need leg surgery.' I also saw the Navy Corpsman for therapy on my knee and back as well as the Dental Assistant, who did excellent work on a cap. The back pain wasn't major.

On Windward, when I wasn't on 12-hour radio duty shift in the COC (Command Operations Center), they might 'farm' me out for various Infantry tasks like alerts or mortar drills. I remember working a punishing schedule of long hours, like 60-80 hour weeks. They were always calling me in to fill in for people. I was able to qualify on the 9mm pistol and shotgun while at Gitmo. On Windward, during one drill, I manned a 50-cal position with two other Marines and we were there till daybreak. It was where we were going to make our 'Last Stand' if the real war showed up. RSC-Windward seemed to have decent Forward Observers. I was given a 'Morse Code' exam when I was a radio operator. It wasn't even the MOS I signed up for, but I liked Radio Operator. I held a Secret Clearance. I raised the colors at Marine Barracks at least once and I considered this a small honor.

My call sign in Cuba for Marine Barracks Command Operations Center was 'Cherokee' and my nickname since the time of SOI-West was 'Chaos'. Montgomery worked the 'switch' as a radio operator at RSC-Leeward and one time he told me when he had been in Ranger School during Florida phase that he was present when the four West Point cadets died of hypothermia in the swamps and had held one in his arms during the lad's dying moments. He said he had fought in Desert Storm with the 3rd Ranger Battalion and it seemed there were other Desert Storm Veterans at Gitmo as well. I was also told Montgomery had a Colombian wife. We kept the phone number for Atlantic Fleet posted on the COC wall, and if there was ever a need, Naval or Marine Air Support could be called in from Florida, etc., in dire emergencies. Marine Sgt's attached to Minefield Maintenance were often asking to take out the shotgun and I always obliged. There's was a dangerous job- demining, etc. I remember one time on the Leeward side when Capt. Petrucci, fully holstering a loaded pistol, was interviewing a male Cuban Asylum Seeker (CAS), who looked slightly tired and dehydrated, and it dawned on me for a moment, that whatever the Cuban stated to Petrucci would have fateful consequences for his desire to enter the USA. Many are called, but few are chosen!

On Armed Forces TV, they ran righteous commercials for Army Special Forces, stating: 'Special men, with Special skills, for Special missions- that's why they call them Special Forces!' while laughingly showing a Vietnamese-American wearing his Green Beret in an obvious allusion to the Vietnam War, where the Green Berets cut their teeth. City Colleges of Chicago offered college courses to service members on-base, and many Marines and Navy folks elected to take advantage. They sold Jamaican cigars at the local Leeward branch of the NEX, but it was difficult to get Cuban cigars but some Marines magically produced them. There were Jamaican workers on the base, not all cleared to be there. There were also daily visits by older Cuban workers (mostly women) through the North East Gate of the base, and they handled menial tasks, like custodian.

There was a story about Pfc. Plough and Pfc. Zimmerman on a MOP, when Plough 'went off his bonkers' and shot rounds across the fenceline at a buzzard flying near the tower. Both Zimmerman and Plough were reprimanded for this, especially Plough. Col. Bamford called the Cuban side to alleviate tensions. I couldn't figure out why Zimmerman took the fall. Also, I remember when a story came through the COC that drug runners had been spotted by our Intelligence and a message was passed to the Venezuelan Coast Guard, who subsequently 'blew away' the watercraft en route headed north to the Caribbean islands or Florida. Also, I remember when a couple and their child showed up at the bottom of a MOP (Marine Observation Post) on July 4th, asking for Asylum. This was kind of a cute story to the Marines at Gitmo. Also, I remember when a Cuban Master Sgt. got wind he was going to be sacked by the communists and he decided to swim along the border from Cuba to 'Gitmo' where he sought asylum in America.

I remember when Galaz told us that a 'react' team had spotted a male CAS (Cuban Asylum Seeker) in the middle of the no-man's land and a mine detonated near him, causing him to be cut in half. He was just waving at a shadow or haze of flies going up and down near him, while he remained pretty much a bloody mess. Galaz saw all this threw his TOW scope. I assume this individual passed. We also did a mortar shoot on New Year's Eve and marched to the Leeward side with pride. We had provided a nice fireworks show over the bay for civilians and DoD personnel alike. But one must be careful. The bravest creatures on Gitmo aren't the Marines, but the various herds of banana rats residing on the base. These fearless rodents display a remarkable temerity whenever Humvees cruise the dusty dirt roads, popping their heads up right in front of a vehicle with little regard for life and limb. Col. Bamford even had us perform riot training and it literally turned into thrashing. Now and then, I would ride 'shotgun' with the Line NCO in his Humvee, helping distribute chow to the Marines on duty.

One time we were doing a night patrol near the fenceline on the Leeward side, and we approached a barbed wire fence, began climbing over it, and I whispered to one of my buddies, 'What if its a minefield?' Such minefields did exist on our side of the fenceline and were constantly being demined by our people. The patrol stopped for a moment, reorientated a little bit, and then continued on. Luckily nothing bad happened. There was also an incident when a male Cuban Asylum seeker arrived unexpected, to say the least, at the Leeward Marine BOQ (Bachelor's Officer Quarters), and presented himself, innocently enough, to a Marine 2nd Lt., at his open front door, in the midst of the Lt's morning shave. A surprize to say the least! Also, one time, we were riding in a back of a Deuce and a half truck (that was open on the back) at the end of our shift on the fenceline and I noticed tiny footprints leading from the No-Man's Land onto our side of the base. Yet no one had radioed about an intruder. Did one slip threw the cracks? Another time, myself and another young Marine were relieved by two other Marines and our shift was over, but instead of waiting for a ride back we decided to walk back a few miles to the Leeward company area. It was a georgeous, sunny day in Gitmo and I was feeling good about life!

Another time on the fenceline, I was serving with Bennett, a 'dark' Marine, and he had decided to use his 'down' time to fish at the bottom of the MOP (likely 13) along the Camaneira River and while standing atop the MOP holding my weapon, I noticed a bright green 'blur' approach his line from under the water. It grabbed the line, Bennett struggled for a number of seconds, and then it snapped the line and departed. We thought it may have been a nurse shark. What a fish story!

One time, Capt. Jewell came into the radio room and ordered me to call Col. Bamford and the XO and tell them immediately that the U.S. Embassies had been attacked in Kenya and Tanzania. I did just that. They were afraid we might get attacked too. I remember viewing, through binoculars, Chinese and Russian freighters visiting Cuba. This was one of my duties to observe them. The huge ships would come in right through the middle of the bay. I also remember viewing a young Cuban woman riding her bicycle in the early morning mist on the perimeter road south of Caimanera City; Cuba. I was so used to seeing Cuban soldiers, BMP's, jeeps, small aircraft, or even the occasional report of a tank, but never a civilian! We stood opposite the Cuban Frontier Brigade. I remember sitting on a MOP (Marine Observation Post), with my legs over the top of the tower, while watching a buzzard (looked like an eagle) doing gentle slopes near me. I felt happy to be serving America!

We once visited the base open-air theatre and saw 'American Werewolf in Paris.' Military bases sure do seem like a small slice of America. Moreover, I was present during a 'Bad Boys' waterslide party when Marines would toss military dependent children down the slide! Music was just blaring. The kids loved it and had fun! Moreover, Marines dressed up 'spiffy', many in dress blues, for the Marine Corps Birthday Party on November 10, 1775, with a handsome, frosted, cake present. a Senior NCO gave a rousing speech, stating emphatically, 'There's something about being American! I was present on the Windward side of Gitmo when Hurricane George hit in 1998 and there was some windy, howling hours as the Hurricane ripped through. I was in the barracks at this time and they gave me only one MRE (meal-ready-to-eat) for that whole day. I participated in the Annual 'Gitmo' Poetry Contest for 1998 and was proud of my entry. In addition, I remember watching World Cup soccer matches while sitting in the Windward chow hall, notably when Holland won a big game. I was also present during 100th Anniversary celebrations of the Spanish-American War, when officers and historians gave fine speeches. We were also onbase on Gitmo when Pope John Paul II held Mass for the Communists and Catholics alike- a historic moment for Cuba.

La Count told me one time regarding Jury that 'They always got something going about Kaess.' His statement almost made me feel uneasy. It didn't help when Riley insulted me one time out of nowhere, but I brushed it aside. Snow received Non-Judicial Punishment or NJP (Article 15), otherwise known as 'office hours' during his tenure and Jury almost followed suit with me but I refused to sign the papers. I managed to hang in there.

My penpals were Marys Desaulniers (from Canada), Kathy, a teacher from Texas who encouraged me to teach ESL again, my Bible teacher Theresa Sohn, whose gift of suasaes during SOI West was most appreciated, and Ya-Lan, an Asian girl living in Boston, as well as Tisha Stapleton, a sweet Christian girl from West Virginia. There was also an Army Reserve chick who I had met in Albany, New York on leave. All this support was most appreciated. It certainly beat the 'Dear John' Letter I received from Kim Ryung of Pusan, South Korea, when I was going through Boot Camp in MCRD San Diego. I also received slight email from my former girlfriend and Prom date Jennifer Mundt. I had no word on my ex-wife Ellen Byrd Elliott who I assumed was living in Ohio. There was also correspondence from my brother Garret Kaess, who sent along a nutrition supplement (Chondroitin Sulfate) that proved most helpful, & Chris Aguda, a teenage friend now living in New York. I also sent my brother a check when he was struggling to pay for Graduate School tuition.

Also, I wanted to hand a female Marine Corporal (named Cook) a greeting card because I liked her, but then I realized she was significantly younger and probably wouldn't 'dig it' so I bugged out. I went back to the USA not long after. I socked away quite a bit of money during my time in the service. This proved decisive when I went home to Chicago and was able to transition back to civilian life. I wasn't paid for all of my accrued Leave though, but I made up for it, by staying on base for a two-week Leave.

I did a lot of reading while at Gitmo, picking up books such as Homer's *Odyssey*, *For Those I Loved* by Martin Gray, Plutarch's *Lives*, Solzhenitsyn's *Gulag Archipelago*, and biographies of Bill Clinton and Charlton Heston. I was always in the Learning Resource room or base Library snatching books. I read the Bible a lot too and kept a photo of Sir Laurence Olivier from *Henry V* in my wall locker as a symbol of chivalry. I joked to my brother that Cuba felt like a Fellowship year!

We finished off our tour by taking a jump off a pier in the bay with other Marines watching. We waded a bit, then swam back in soaked cammies to the shore- greeted with handshakes and congratulations. Even Jury shook my hand at the end of my tour. I left the U.S. Naval Base at Guantanamo Bay, Cuba, on about October 9, 1998, and had orders to report to the Medical Company at Camp Lejeune, North Carolina, for final outprocessing from the Marines. In North Carolina, there was a Marine Captain, a Legal or JAD Officer, and a female Corporal who helped square us away for outprocessing. I had a Hispanic roommate at Camp Lejeune who was a member of the Marine Corps Boxing Team. I was discharged on Halloween morning, October 31, 1998. *Semper Fi* to all the Marines I served with!